

STRUCTURE OF LOW VOLTAGE ELECTRICAL NETWORKS

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Abstract

This article contains information about the structure of low-voltage networks, connection scheme, daily load graph, and specific characteristics.

Key words

distribution networks, low voltage, transformer, load graph, single-phase consumers.

Low-voltage power networks are divided into distribution and supply power networks. The distribution part is 6-10 kV power transmission networks connected to power transformers in step-down substations. 35-110/6-10 kV substations and distribution networks serve as the power source of low-voltage networks. The 6-10 kV distribution network consists of three-wire conductors with a length from hundreds of meters to tens of kilometers, insulated from the ground. They are supplied from 110-35/10-6 kV substations. These networks provide 6-10/0.4 kV transformer points [1, 2].

One or two transformers with a capacity of 25-1000 kVA depending on the power supply reliability category are used at the transformer points. The high and low voltage sides have a connection group of "star-to-star-zero" (Y/Y-0) and "delta-to-star-zero" (D/Y-0).

Figure 1.1. Options for building low-voltage power networks:
a) highway; b) radial; c) mixed

Networks with a voltage of 0.4 kV are directly connected to the neutral ground and are carried out with SIP, open cable conductors on reinforced concrete, concrete, wooden supports according to the main, radial or mixed scheme. is increased (Fig. 1.1). It can have four or five wires, where there are three phases, one neutral and a wire for street lights. The neutral wire is connected to the ground after 200-300 meters in the sections of the electric network. The cross-sectional area of the neutral wire in low-voltage electrical networks should be greater than that of the phase wires.

The specific characteristics of low-voltage power networks are their continuous development due to the constant growth of consumption, the variety of household electricity receivers and the appearance of new equipment, as well as the increase in requirements for the quality indicators and reliability of electricity. Currently, according to technical conditions, the power installed by households is set at 3 kW in gasified areas, 4.1 kW in non-gasified areas, depending on the consumer's wishes, the maximum power consumption can be set up to $P = 15$ kW.

Another feature of low-voltage power networks is that the daily load schedule is variable and depends on many factors, living conditions, family work schedule,

the level of saturation with electricity receivers, in addition, it depends on the day of the week, also depends on the season (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Daily downloads graph.

The specific characteristics of low-voltage power networks include the need to supply a large number of single-phase consumers with electricity distributed over a large area. As a result, low-voltage electrical networks are characterized by a large length and low load density (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Scheme of the location of supports of low-voltage electrical networks

In short, when designing low-voltage networks, it is necessary to install the transformer point in the load center, taking into account the location of the consumers there, the development, and the objects that can be newly developed. During the study, in many cases, the location of the transformer point was not set to the center of loads (Fig. 3). In the supply of high-quality electricity to consumers, it is important to evenly distribute it among the phases, taking into account the characteristics and capacities of consumers.

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